
Assessment of Products from Nigerian Composite Flours for Local Consumption and Sustainability of Food Culture
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ABSTRACT

The culture of people in every climate around the globe is embedded in their food and food consumption pattern, clothing, language and other aspects of material culture. This study observes the need to prevent perpetual consumption of junk foods from synthetic sources by upgrading the processing of flours from locally available cereals and tubers for sustainable consumption. The study was carried out to produce composite flour for bread making from wheat, soya, maize and cassava to reduce the money spent on importation of wheat into the country through alternative flours. Flours from the local grains and tubers were combined using different ratio in the production of bread. Products were subjected to level of acceptability by thirty respondents, 10 senior civil servants (5 males, 5 females), 10 junior civil servants (5 males, 5 females) and 10 students (5 males, 5 females). Seven hedonic scales were used to determine acceptability of appearance, texture, taste, flavor and overall acceptability. Data was analyzed using frequency tables, percentages and bar charts. Results on acceptability test show that wheat-soya beans bread (sample B) had the highest percentage (100%) in all the organoleptic test followed by wheat bread (Sample A) (96.67%). Based on the findings it was recommended that the Federal Government of Nigeria should encourage flour millers and bakeries in the country to include 20% soya flour into 80% wheat flour for production of bread and other confectionary products. Farmers should be encouraged to plant soya beans in large quantities.

Keywords: Bread, Food culture, Nigerian composite flour, Local foods, Sustainability

Introduction

Bread is a well-established and popular convenience food in Africa for both urban and rural communities (Ituen and Ituen, 2011). It is a staple food prepared by baking dough of flour and water and other additional ingredients such as butter, salt and yeast to improve the taste. Wheat is the most important staple food crop for more than one third of the world's diet than any other cereal crop (Kumar, 2011). It is nutritious, easy to store, transport and can be processed into various types of food. Wheat is considered a good source of minerals, B-group vitamins and dietary fiber, which makes it an excellent health building food. Wheat flour is used to prepare bread, produce biscuit, confectionary products, noodles and so on. The key characteristics which have given it an advantage over other temperate crops is the unique properties of dough formed from wheat flours. This property is the gluten, which form elastic dough with air sacks (Kumar, 2011). Wheat flour is the most important product of wheat milling and is used in the baking and confectionary industries and for home cooking.

Soya bean (*glycine max*) is specie of legume native to East Asia, widely grown for its edible bean which has numerous uses. It is classified as an oil seed rather than a pulse by the UN Food and Agricultural Organization. Soya bean has long been

recognized as a plant, relatively high in protein and have been historically called "meat of the field" (Food Agriculture Organisation, FAO, 2012).

Soya flour refers to crushed soybeans ground finely enough to pass through a hundred-mesh or small screen where special care was taken during desolventizing (not toasted) to minimize denaturation of the protein to retain a high protein dispensability index. All soy flours are 50% protein and give a protein boost to recipes (Yanez, 1992).

As explained by Williams and Akiko (2007), soy flour can be divided into three types based on their method of production namely; whole soy flour, mechanically extracted soy flour and solvent extracted soy flour. The whole soy flour can also be referred to as "full-fat soy flour". It is the most natural and lightly-processed product, containing all of the oil naturally presents in soybeans, it typically contains 18-20% protein. To produce whole soy flour, whole soybeans are steamed, dried, cracked, dehulled and ground. It can be made relatively simple in an inexpensive technology which makes whole soy flour to be generally considered to have a better flavour when considered to others.

Mechanically extracted soy flour is made by grinding the low fat press cake from soya beans that have been crushed, steamed, and hydraulic or

expeller pressed to extract their oil containing typically 5-8% fat, it is no longer widely produced in most industrialized countries. Solvent extracted soy flour is made by grinding the defatted flakes of meal remaining after removing the oil from crushed soya beans using hexane (a typical petroleum based solvent) or other chemical solvents, examples includes: defatted soy flour, low-fat soy flour, high-fat soy flour, lecithinated soy flour, enzyme active soy flour.

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) is extensively cultivated as annual crop in tropical and subtropical regions for its edible starchy, tuberous root. Cassava is a major source of carbohydrates and it is the third largest source of food carbohydrates in the tropics, it is a major staple food in the developing world (IITA, 2005). Cassava provides a basic diet for about 50 million people and is one of the most drought tolerant crops capable of growing on marginal soils (Oyewole, 2002).

Nigeria is the world's largest producer of cassava, cassava root is a good source of carbohydrate but a poor source of protein. A predominantly cassava root diet can cause protein energy malnutrition (PEM). It contains anti-nutrition factors and toxins (FAO, 2004), therefore, it must be properly prepared before consumption. Improper preparation of cassava can leave residual cyanide which can lead to intoxication and goiters as well as partial paralysis.

High quality cassava flour is made within a day of harvesting the root. The cassava flour is very white, has low fat content and is not sour like traditional fermented cassava flour, it does not give a bad smell or taste to food products (Centre of Agricultural and Rural Cooperation, 2007). Cassava flour can mix well with wheat flour for use in breads or cakes (Padamaja, 2008). Most countries in Africa including Nigeria depend almost entirely on imported wheat for bread market. All soy flours is 50% protein and gives a protein boost to recipes (Yanez, 1992). These prominent cassava producing African countries import about 2 million of wheat yearly for the baking industry (Ituen and Ituen, 2011). A lot of foreign

exchange is expended in this exercise. Therefore, this study compared bread made from wheat flour, wheat and soy flour and wheat and cassava flour to reduce the amount been spent on importing wheat flour to the country and also to increase protein content of wheat flour by addition of soya flour.

Methodology

Bread samples were prepared in Food and Nutrition Laboratory of Home Economics Department in Adeyemi College of Education Ondo, Ondo State following the processing of soya beans into soy flour as recommended by William and Akiko (2007) and processing of cassava root into cassava flour as recommended by Centre for Agricultural and Rural Cooperation, CTA, (2007). The method that was used in preparing the three bread samples is the straight-dough method whereby all the ingredients in bread formulation were mixed to form developed homogenous dough in one step (Sahlstrom and Brathen, 1997). Flour and other ingredients like butter, sugar, yeast, flavour, salt, water among others were mixed, kneaded, proofed and baked to produce bread.

The three samples of bread produced were in the following ratios:

Sample	Wheat flour (%)	Soy flour (%)	Cassava flour (%)
A	100	0	0
B	80	20	0
C	80	0	20

The bread samples were given to thirty (30) randomly selected respondents (fifteen (15) male and fifteen (15) female) who are consumers of bread and were served with each bread sample with tea (lipton in milk), and mayonnaise. The respondents were given acceptability forms to express their views on the appearance, taste, texture, flavour and level of acceptability of the three bread samples. An acceptability form rated in seven (7) hedonic scales was administered to the selected respondents.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Dislikes, Intermediate and Likes of Bread Sample A

Variables	Dislikes (%)	Intermediate (%)	Likes (%)	Total (%)
Appearance	3.33	0.00	96.67	100.00
Texture	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00
Taste	3.33	0.00	96.67	100.00
Flavour	3.33	0.00	96.67	100.00
Acceptability	3.33	0.00	96.67	100.00

Table 2: Dislikes, Intermediate and Likes of Bread Sample B

Variables	Dislikes (%)	Intermediate (%)	Likes (%)	Total (%)
Appearance	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00
Texture	0.00	3.33	96.67	100.00
Taste	0.00	3.33	96.67	100.00
Flavour	0.00	3.33	96.67	100.00
Acceptability	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00

Table 3: Dislikes, Intermediate and Likes of Bread Sample C

Variables	Dislikes (%)	Intermediate (%)	Likes (%)	Total (%)
Appearance	36.67	0.00	63.33	100.00
Texture	23.33	3.33	73.33	100.00
Taste	40.00	10.00	50.00	100.00
Flavour	43.33	6.67	50.00	100.00
Acceptability	30.00	0.00	60.00	100.00

Table 4: Comparison of Acceptability of Bread Samples A, B and C

Variables	Sample A			Sample B			Sample C		
	Dislike	Intermediate	Like	Dislike	Intermediate	Like	Dislike	Intermediate	Like
Appearance	3.33	0.00	96.67	0.00	0.00	100.00	36.67	0.00	63.33
Texture	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	3.33	96.67	23.33	3.33	73.33
Taste	3.33	0.00	96.67	0.00	3.33	96.67	40.00	10.00	50.00
Flavour	3.33	0.00	96.67	0.00	3.33	96.67	43.33	6.67	50.00
Acceptability	3.33	0.00	96.67	0.00	0.00	100.00	30.00	10.00	60.00

Discussion of Findings

It is clear from the tables afore presented that bread baked with 20% soy flour and 80% wheat flour (Sample B) was rated higher with 100% in appearance, 96.67% in texture, 96.67% in taste, 96.67% and 100% in flavour and general acceptability and respondents preferred to buy it than 100% wheat flour bread. Yanez (1992) stated that several changes occurred with the incorporation of soy flour to wheat flour such as increase in water absorption and weakening of dough, higher levels of substitution produced an increase stickiness of the dough that made its handling more difficult. Yanez

(1992) also explained that bread containing soy flour is slightly darker than wheat bread with score of 71 points in a scale of 100.

Wheat bread 100% (Sample A) was rated the second most acceptable by the respondents, through 96.67% in appearance, 100% in texture, 96.67% in taste, 96.67% in flavour and general acceptability. Kumar (2011) stated that, globally there is no doubt that the number of people who rely on wheat bread for substantial part of their diet amount to several billions.

Wheat flour (80%) with cassava flour (20%) bread (Sample C) was the least accepted by the respondents based on the findings with 63.33% in

appearance, 73.33% in texture, 50% in taste, 50% and 60% respectively in flavour and general acceptability test. The Federal Institute of Industrial Research (2005) concluded in an investigation that cassava flour can be successfully mixed with wheat flour for bread at varying levels of substitution; 10-15% being the most acceptable for bread making, while 15-20% is acceptable for confectionaries and other baked products.

There was no observable difference between wheat bread and wheat-soy bread (most of the bread characteristics, appearance, texture, taste, flavour) were positive and accepted by consumers. Ugwuona *et al.* (2012) narrated in a study carried out on chemical and sensory quality of cakes formulated with wheat, soy bean and cassava flours that soy flours had the highest protein and fat content and the sensory scores indicated that wheat-soy cakes has the highest acceptability from the panel of judges. There was an observable difference between wheat bread, wheat-soy bread and wheat-cassava bread in terms of sensory qualities; appearance, texture, taste and flavour. Watter *et al.* (2004) explained that most of the previous studies conducted on the use of cassava in wheat flour for bread making purposes were devoted to determining the effect of biological origin of flour and level of wheat flour substitution on their bread making quality. They generally observed reduction in loaf volume and impairment of sensory qualities i.e. appearance, texture and flavour as the level of substitution of wheat and non-wheat flour increased. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the quality of composite cassava-wheat bread.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the integration of soy flour in wheat bread production is a widely acceptable innovation by consumers. Wheat-soy bread has better texture, appearance, taste and flavour when compared with wheat bread and wheat-cassava bread. A lot of foreign exchange is expended in importing wheat year for the baking industry

Recommendations

- Awareness should be created on the importance of soy flour and its complementation of wheat flour in confectionary product

- Farmers should be encouraged to plant soya beans in large quantities

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